

Facebook Digital Market Platforms - Information that Facilitates Purchase Decisions

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Abstract

Introduction: Facebook groups are commonly being used as a marketing platform to buy/sell their products these days, even though the real purpose of Facebook groups is to provide a place/platform to connect with people who share common interests and help to build their communities of similar interests. Because of this, this paper refers to these Facebook buy-and-sell groups as "Digital Market Platforms" (DMPs) because people often turn these Facebook groups into buying and selling products/services and play both buyer and seller roles.

Objectives: This paper's primary objective is to examine the methods by which Bangladeshi sellers disclose information about their products and to pinpoint the questions/queries/FAQs that support customers' decision-making process when making purchases from DMPs.

Methods: A total of 80 sales posts from 10 Facebook DMPs are analyzed to determine what customers want to know before placing an order from those platforms. Between January 15, 2021, and March 5, 2021, from the selected 10 Facebook DMPs, a total of 80 popular posts' product descriptions (from the caption) are collected to analyse the product-related information-sharing tendency of the Bangladeshi sellers as well as their customer comments' to analyse the common queries of the Bangladeshi customers following the passive analysis methodology. In addition, sellers and customers are divided into two groups based on their gender, and a comparison is made between male and female sellers as well as customers. The 620 comments are then generalized into 12 common queries based on their true meanings and illustrated in the findings section. In addition, tables, bar graphs, and pie charts are used to analyze the other findings more clearly based on gender distribution.

Findings: Findings section provide information from both seller and customer perspectives. The majority of Bangladeshi sellers included information about the price they are seeking for their products in the caption of their posts. Unfortunately, there are fewer posts where sellers give enough details about their products. In comparison to female sellers, male sellers are found to sell electronic products more frequently, mention the price in between asking/fixed mode, and provide sufficient information in the caption of their posts. Female sellers, on the other hand, are more prevalent on female-focused platforms, where they sell used or unused women's products like clothing and cosmetics as well as encourage customers to message them privately to know more about their posted products. From the customer perspective, Bangladeshi customers mostly ask about price and bargaining, Male customers mostly bargain, mock, write irrelevant and negative comments, inquire about products and whether products are available, and seek exchange offers on Facebook DMPs, whereas female customers mostly ask price-related questions only. Moreover, a tendency among females is also observed that they are more likely to inquire about products via private messages. In comparison to female customers, males prefer to recommend products by tagging their Facebook friends. The study suggests sellers provide sufficient information regarding their products/services and customers to ask queries more where necessary in order to make purchase decisions more easily in future.

Keywords: Facebook buy & sells group; Digital Market Platform; Purchase Decision Making; Bangladeshi Customers' Purchase Behavior; Common Queries; Common FAQ.

1. Introduction

The digital platform can be thought of as the sum of the total space for the exchange of information, products, or services between producers and customers, as well as the platform that communicates with them. It is important to understand that the community itself is a necessary part of the digital platform without that community the underlying value of the digital platform is very low (Watts, 2020).

A Digital Market Platform (DMP) refers to an online platform that connects buyers and sellers through a distributor's website or app where the platform acts as a digital intermediary, bringing buyers and sellers together

to transact efficiently (Gatautis, 2017). Moreover, here, the platform is a website or application that facilitates shopping online from many different sources. It should be noted here that the market platform operator has no inventory, their job is to approve other people's product posts to a user and facilitate a transaction. Buyers can choose what to buy, and sellers get a variety of customers to sell to (Kestenbaum, 2017).

In Bangladesh, Facebook is the most popular social media site. According to Napoleoncat.com, as of January 2021, Bangladesh's population was 165.5 million while there were 45.4 million Facebook users in Bangladesh, which represented 26.5% of its total population. Most of them were men who made up 69.4% of the total population. Individuals between the ages of 18 and 24 made up the largest user group (19.7 million). The separation of gender is also important while understanding sales and purchase intention. Jayawardena et al. (2007) found that gender has a significant influence on online purchase intent. By incorporating the concept of gender into the study of the relationship between purchasing orientations and the customer's online purchase intention, it may be able to enrich existing literature. This growing number of users have helped to grow the DMPs of Facebook such as buy and sell groups where buyers and sellers either from a common community or from different community interact with each other. The platforms are also highly popular for customer-to-customer social commerce as well, where customers sell/exchange their used products with other customers by sharing a post on these platforms so that interested customers get to know about their products. Although there are lots of DMPs that have high numbers of users due to a lack of monitoring and awareness among the users, these groups can't be successful. Moreover, as the DMPs involve distinctive types of buyers and sellers out of our own Facebook friend list, it's quite difficult to trust the seller and order a product just by seeing the product's post. That is why customers usually comment on the products post to assure on several things that they believe make sure of before placing an order. Realizing the evolving opportunities of future business, the study focuses on how Bangladeshis are posting their product posts for sale and what questions help them make purchasing decisions.

This study analyzes Facebook's DMP from both Bangladeshi customers' and sellers' perspectives. It focuses on the ways sellers publish their product posts and the ways customers interact on the DMPs when they decide to purchase any products from these platforms. Especially, the study mainly is going to focus on the DMP that is offered by the social networking site 'Facebook'. It allows buyers and sellers to list new, used or old items, services and offers and promote them directly within the groups. The groups also allow sellers to reach thousands of people through the connection of these platforms, while also allowing Facebook friends, who are connected to the platforms, to notify that their friend has listed a product to sell or has commented on a product's post. Therefore, the study has been prepared to analyze the ways Bangladeshi sellers publish their sales posts and the ways customers interact with those sales posts of these Facebook DMPs.

1.1 Significance

The popularity of the DMP is increasing and the platforms will get more attention from customers and sellers every day as they hold a huge amount of customers in one place who have more or less similar interests. A very popular Bangladeshi online market platform called '**Recycle Bin**', for example, shares a common platform that allows Bangladeshi sellers and buyers to sell and buy their second-hand goods at a discounted price. Surprisingly, the platform started its journey on October 5, 2020, and in those six consecutive months, the members of the Recycle Bin have reached a million and all members have joined by agreeing to the group rules that they will share, sell and buy used items at a reduced price. From this example, it is clear that the DMP is going to be attractive for marketers and businesses to understand the customer's intentions and decision-making factors. In addition, today's business organizations can orchestrate a concrete communication platform to enable customers to reach the business organization at the right time. Sellers' information-sharing tendency and customers' comments and inquiries are the most essential Sellers in understanding customers and their needs. When customers ask questions and wait for their feedback but don't get the desired response, they get

frustrated and may no longer have the desire for the product. However, majority of the Bangladeshi companies do not focus on these limitations and as a consequence, lose a huge number of customers. With this in mind, this study aims to help marketers use search queries and identify customer queries to learn how to predict common queries from Bangladeshi customers on the DMP. Moreover, the study will provide a meaningful understanding of how to approach the promotion of a product and how customers interact, show interest, and make decisions on the DMP, as customers today increasingly show their interest in buying products from these Facebook DMPs.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Overview of Digital Market Platform (DMP)

The digital platform can be thought of as the sum of the total space for the exchange of information, products, or services between producers and customers, as well as the platform that communicates with them. It is important to understand that the community itself is a necessary part of the digital platform without that community the underlying value of the digital platform is very low (Watts, 2020).

A DMP refers to a digital platform that connects buyers and sellers through a distributor's website or app where the platform acts as a digital intermediary, bringing buyers and sellers together to transact efficiently (Gatautis, 2017). Moreover, here, the platform is a website or application that facilitates shopping online from many different sources. It should be noted here that the market platform operator has no inventory, their job is to approve other people's product posts to a user and facilitate a transaction. Buyers can choose what to buy, and sellers get a variety of customers to sell to (Kestenbaum, 2017).

Greer. A., (2020) published an article in *Fashion Journal* named "The unwritten rules of the Facebook buy/sell group" where he described Facebook buying/selling groups, which can also be identified as an online market platform, are set up by the general Facebook users to create a community so that members can buy and sell niche items selected by the group's admins and moderators. These groups are governed by the rules of what can be sold and then users can post their items to other users to buy/bid (Isogtek.com, 2020). The Facebook market platform offered by the social networking site is a free service. It allows sellers to list different new, used, or old items, services and offers and promote them directly within the quick community. The platforms also allow sellers to reach thousands of people through their social networks, while also allowing Facebook friends to introduce you to others. Sellers can sell any item or service that meets community policy. Like advertisements, buyers can contact sellers by commenting in the comments section or boxing in messaging, inspecting the merchandise, and setting pricing, shipping, and other details (123trick.com, 2019).

Facebook business pages, Facebook marketplaces, and Facebook stores often confuse people (Git, 2020). A Facebook business page is a free opportunity for companies, organizations, and brands to raise brand awareness of the business and generate sales on Facebook. The Facebook Store, a business group created by individual brands or sellers, is for sellers who have products to sell to the public by inviting them to a platform where customers have no chance of selling back. However, The Facebook DMP is a free service offered by Facebook that allows its members to open Facebook groups and use the platform to buy and sell products and services within their local community. These platforms consist of both buyers and sellers and are controlled by admin/moderators. Anyone can buy and sell directly on the platform maintaining the group/platforms rules and regulations. However, there is no Facebook payment system on the platform (Facebook and commerce, 2020).

However, in today's competitive market, Facebook's market platforms have become very popular as sellers and buyers from similar communities can buy and sell their products in one place. Groups are often separated into by-product categories such as cars, bicycles, cosmetics, clothing, etc. Customers and sellers find it very friendly and always return to these groups because these platforms have very specific goals to explore their ideal target market. No other marketing platform rarely allows such great efficiency (How small

businesses, 2018). According to the article of [DhakaTribune.com \(2018\)](#) named “How small businesses use Facebook to promote products and services”, the DMP varied products, communities, societies, social classes and many other ways. Several Bangladeshi platforms can be found on Facebook only for iPhone accessories where android users are requested not to join. Just like this, there are lots of groups for motorbikes, cars, smartphones, cosmetic products, and clothing. Sellers can only sell their products and accessories according to the group types on the platforms. In addition, a lot of market platform also exists based on the district of Bangladesh (i.e. Sylhet buy and sell, Rajshahi Shopping). Nevertheless, by means of protection, Facebook restricts the sale of items like animals, drugs, weapons, counterfeits and other items that infringe intellectual property rights on its market platforms or Marketplace.

2.2 Benefits achieved by Bangladeshi people using the DMPs

Facebook's market platform offers unique features to buyers and sellers that not all mainstream social media platforms have. Facebook DMPs are made up of people with almost the same type of interests at heart ([Hutchinson, 2016](#)). These interests can be movies, gadgets, smartphones, bikes, cars, music, food, specials, etc.

These platforms are convenient for customers in Bangladesh as these platforms are separated into different groups for different interests. As a user with more than one interest, Bangladeshi customers can join different DMPs based on their interests and find updates on all their necessary products ([Facebook and commerce, 2020](#)). In addition, DMPs are like marketplaces where Bangladeshi users can meet and socialize in the common interest of simply buying and selling. These platforms are exclusively intended for buying and selling and any other activity carried out could be considered abusive ([Zabeen, Ara & Sarwar, 2013](#)).

Several Bangladeshi entrepreneurs are now enjoying the benefits of these DMPs. As customers join markets based on their interests. They are capable to analyze the markets, and entrepreneurs can promote and offer their products. Most of these products are often bought by wholesalers for retail on these market platforms where there are already many potential buyers of these products. According to the [DhakaTribune \(2018\)](#) article, small businesses and entrepreneurs are currently using Facebook to promote, advertise and sell products, and also reach its privileged customers. Being a very accessible platform for everyone, the products can be found, viewed, and delivered to a large community of customers. The companies on the Facebook DMPs are currently reshaping their conventional marketing methods, as these businesses do not need formal space or manpower to operate. students can simply open a page and start selling their products to known friends and relatives, which spreads further through their colleagues and acquaintances, hence their businesses boom ([How small business, 2018](#)). From another previous research conducted by [Tabassum, \(2018\)](#), it appears that middle-aged married women who have graduated tend to become entrepreneurs. Most of the time, they choose casual shopping and clothing, food, and a variety of items to start their business. Most of these entrepreneurs use F-commerce and Facebook DMPs as their sole source of income and receive their sales payments either through bKash or cash on delivery. Moreover, [Tabassum](#) identified nine factors, such as work-life balance, interpersonal skills, personal and relationship skills, purchasing skills, management skills, entrepreneurial skills, intrinsic motivation, enthusiasm, and ease of use. She defined these factors as success factors for female entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, Facebook's DMPs also help Bangladeshi customers to sell things they no longer need on Facebook. Personal items or old tech, half-junkies, or something they just can't seem to impress could be sold on these platforms. With the huge number of people on Facebook's DMP, it is very easy to find a Bangladeshi buyer for almost anything that Bangladeshi sellers want to sell ([Facebook and commerce, 2020](#)).

To make purchasing decisions, online platforms allow users to connect with their peers by adding them to a network of friends, facilitating communication, especially between peers ([Ahuja and Galvin 2003](#)). Online groups have a significant impact on customer behaviour and purchasing intentions and implicit purchasing decisions. For example, social networking sites provide a public forum that allows individual customers to

express their voices and access product information (through comments) that helps them make purchasing decisions (Kozinets et al., 2010). Labrecque (2014) mentioned that as brands (like sellers) use social media platforms to consolidate their position, customer expectations are increasingly high, which is why they encourage the establishment of technology to help the process of manufacturing. Social media allows marketers to maintain direct contact with customers. In addition, Park and Kim (2003) identified the key factors that affect the purchasing behaviour of users and mentioned that the information satisfaction of any product includes knowledge about its related functions, the recommendation and evaluation of the user. To meet the information needs of users, the information must be competent and sufficient to help customers make decisions and represent content reliably.

3. Methods

3.1 Research approach

According to the research conducted by Creswell (2014), qualitative research is primarily exploratory research. It is used to understand the underlying causes, opinions, and motivations. Provides insight into issues or helps develop ideas or hypotheses for potential quantitative research.

As the title of this study is "Facebook Digital Market Platforms - Information that facilitates purchase decisions", a total of 10 Facebook DMPs are observed and a total of 80 product posts (8 posts per platform) are analyzed to identify the common questions for Bangladeshi customers when they decide to purchase from any market platform. Therefore, the research can be described as exploratory research, mainly focusing on qualitative research methods to explain problem ideas to develop an understanding between sellers depending on genders and disclose the common queries of customers. In addition, the study will include tables and charts to show gender-wise distribution.

3.2 Data collection methods

The qualitative research methods of social media can be described in three ways: active analysis, passive analysis, and self-identification research (Eysenbach & Till, 2001). Passive analysis on Facebook involves information patterns or interactions between users observed on Facebook Research in existing Facebook groups. For example, Kent et al. (2016), used a Facebook keyword search to determine public attitudes towards obesity and cancer to identify relevant topics, grammatical elements, and emotional value contained in Facebook posts and related comments.

Similarly, data of this study are collected via passive analysis (direct observation) from 10 different Facebook DMPs without the users' consent to identify the information shared by the sellers while posting product posts.

3.3 Sample descriptions

A total of 80 posts from 10 Facebook DMPs are analyzed to determine what customers want to know before placing an order on that platform. The market platform is chosen based on its popularity, customer response, and engagement based on post comments. Besides that, there are thousands of Facebook DMPs with a large number of product posts published each day, but these platforms are not chosen for the study due to a lack of customer response in their posts' comments section. Sample comments are gathered from posts approved between January 15, 2021, and March 5, 2021, on the 10 market platforms (see Table 7 for more details about the platforms), as well as from posts in which customers comment on their queries. The sample population is described in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Sample description

Facebook Market platform List	Total Posts	Total Comments	Male Comments	Female Comments
1. Recycle Bin	8	104	61	43
2. Mobile Buy and Sell Bazar	8	127	122	5

3. Used Unused Products Sell	8	40	0	40
4. Buy And Sell Bangladesh	8	138	2	136
5. GPU Market Bangladesh - Buy/Sell/Trade	8	57	57	0
6. Buy Sell Exchange (ক্রয়-বিক্রয়-এক্সচেঞ্জ)	8	27	26	1
7. Bd Bike Sell Bazar	8	29	29	0
8. Online Product Sell & Exchange™	8	30	30	0
9. Sell UNLOVED Stuffs ♥	8	24	0	24
10. Used Cars For Sale in Bangladesh (UCSB)	8	44	43	1
Total	80	620	370	250

3.4 Data analysis and interpretation

From the 80 posts, sellers and customers are divided into two (02) groups based on their gender, and a comparison between male and female sellers/customers is drawn. The 80 posts' product descriptions (captions) are then divided into three sections, namely (1) no information at all, (2) insufficient information, and (3) sufficient information, in order to identify the information-sharing tendencies of the Bangladeshi sellers. The 620 comments are then generalized into 12 common queries based on their true meanings and provided in the findings and analysis chapter to interpret them. Furthermore, tables, bar charts, and pie charts are utilized to analyze the findings more clearly based on gender distribution.

4. Findings

The study's findings are based on the 80 posts from the ten (10) mentioned Facebook DMPs (eight posts from each platform). The two main types of analysis are shown here. The first is from the seller's point of view, demonstrating how the seller shared product-related information to assist customers in making purchasing decisions. The second set of results is based on 620 customer comments that are taken as queries and then generalized to present as common queries.

4.1 Sellers' shared information in the product description – Gender-wise comparison

The 80 products post posted on the market platform by the sellers contain different products, but few common ideas are known to help understand the Bangladeshi sellers. The sellers' posts provide two important findings based on the seller's gender distribution and the descriptions of their products.

I. Gender-wise analysis of sellers

Figure 1: Sellers distribution – Gender-wise

After analyzing the 80 posts in *Figure 1*, it is found that the majority of the sellers are male, accounting for 64% or 51 of the total sellers. Female sellers 36% or 29. Note that female sellers are mostly from three female platforms and males are mostly from five market platforms which are for both genders.

Figure 2: Price announced by the sellers

Figure 2 shows the prices of the products mentioned or not mentioned by the sellers as this price is considered the most important factor for the customers to make a purchase decision. It was found that out of 80 sellers, 51 sellers mentioned the price of the product and 29 sellers did not mention the price of the product in their posts.

Table 2: Price announced by sellers – Gender-wise

Price announced by sellers – Gender-wise			
Male sellers		Female Sellers	
Price Mentioned	39	Price Mentioned	12
Price Not Mentioned	12	Price Not Mentioned	17
Total	51	Total	29

Analysis of price declarations based on gender distribution has found significant data. The results of *Table 2* show that male sellers are more interested in providing product price information than female sellers. On the other hand, female sellers are less interested in disclosing their asking price rather they prefer to declare the price through inbox messaging. However, 39 or 76.4% of the 51 male sellers mentioned the price of their products and only 12 or 41.3% of the 29 female sellers mentioned the price of their products in their posts.

II. Product description or caption-wise analysis

The analysis is conducted to identify whether sellers are providing sufficient information to help the customers to receive the actual product's conditions and limitations so that they can decide better before commenting on any queries or making purchase decisions from the Facebook market platform. The captions of the 80 posts are generalized into three parts mentioned in *Table 3* below:

Table 3. 80 posts' captions generalized into three parts

The Ways sellers design posts	Description
i. No information at all	The only caption including the product's name and the price is selected for this segment as this information doesn't provide any product-related info to the customers.
ii. Insufficient Information	A post that reflects the intention of the seller to share product information, but the information is not sufficient for customers to make purchase decisions or to knock the seller via 'inbox' messaging instantly.
iii. Sufficient information	A post that reflects the seller's intention to share as much product-relevant information to customers so that they can instantly take purchase decisions and knock the seller via 'inbox' messaging.

Table 4: The information shared by the sellers – Gender-wise distribution

Gender-wise distribution of the products caption's information			
Male		Female	
No Information at all	7	No Information at all	5
Insufficient Information	16	Insufficient Information	14
Sufficient Information	28	Sufficient Information	10
Total	51	Total	29

Table 4 shows that male sellers provide sufficient information on their product's caption compared to female sellers. Out of 51 male sellers, 54.9% or 28 sellers mentioned sufficient information. On the other hand, out of 29 female sellers, only 34.48% or 10 sellers provided sufficient product-related information on their product's posts which is situated above the product's image on the Facebook DMPs. However, in total 47.5% of sellers shared sufficient information, 37.5% of sellers shared insufficient information, and only 15% of sellers are detected who shared no product's relevant information at all on the product's description area.

4.2 Information sharing tendencies between Bangladeshi male and female sellers on the Facebook DMPs

I. Female sellers: Most of the Bangladeshi female sellers started posting their products with very good wishes, for instance, saying Assalamualaikum, Good Morning, Good Evening, and Hello Friends. But most of them do not share information about the actual product at all. Even so, they share product information that is too inadequate for customers to make decisions. It was also found that female sellers encourage most customers to inbox their questions and customers do not answer the questions asked in the comments section of their posts. Additionally, female sellers focus significantly more on product images than sharing product information and captions and in most cases do not mention prices, delivery schedules, product descriptions, bargaining options, etc. As a result, comment sections are flooded with queries due to a lack of accurate product-specific information. Moreover, they are found selling more either new or used women's clothing and cosmetics products than technological/electronics products such as smartphones, computers, gadgets, and cars. Most of them do not want to disclose their prices publicly and prefer to communicate through 'inbox' messaging.

II. Male Sellers: Male sellers appear to be more organized in publishing product posts than female sellers. Although it is very rare for male sellers to start their captions with any kind of greeting, their posts often contain product-specific information. The analysis found that most male sellers share a sufficient amount of information when they post their products on the Facebook Market Platform so that customers can know about the products when scrolling through the product posts. It was very rare that any male sellers are found selling any type of men's clothing or cosmetic products rather they are mostly found selling electronics/technological products on the Facebook DMPs such as smartphones, computers, laptops, cars, motorbikes, or any other gadgets. Additionally, male customers usually mention the product's price and allow customers to bargain via personal messaging. Often they mention that the price is fixed and no exchange offer is available so that customers can't bargain with the price or comment queries for exchange. Therefore, it is found that male sellers are more straightforward while selling products on Facebook DMPs.

4.3 Common queries of customers on the FMP

The 620 customer questions analyzed in the survey commented under 80 posts on 10 Facebook DMPs. Of course, the comments are different from each other, but all the comments are later generalized into 12 categories as the most common questions of the Facebook Market platform. For example, some customers simply ask 'price?' By commenting on the question for the price of the product, while someone else commented 'how much?' And another wrote 'say the price'; all these price-related queries are taken in a single section called 'Queries for Price'. The findings and observations of common queries that are found from analyzing the 10 market platforms are discussed below in *Table 5*:

Table 5: Number and percentage of each category

Common Queries for Bangladeshi customers	Total	
	comments	Percentages
1. Queries on price	203	32.74%
2. Bargaining	104	16.77%
3. Query for Availability	50	8.06%
4. General Query – product related but other than price, location, exchange options, and availability of the products.	49	7.90%
5. Mocking & Irrelevant	40	6.45%
6. Inbox, Following or interested	37	5.97%
7. Recommendation	34	5.48%
8. The query for exchange – lower products plus cash offers	26	4.19%
9. Positive or supportive comments and product-related Opinion	21	3.39%
10. Promoting own products	21	3.39%

11. Location	18	2.90%
12. Negative comments – Overpriced	17	2.74%
Total	620	100.00

4.3.1 Queries on price

The most common queries asked by Bangladeshi customers are asking about the products' prices on Facebook DMPs. In *Table 5*, out of 620 comments analyzed in this study, 203 are found price-related queries where the customers commented to know the products price. Usually, a post that publishes without listing the product's price is flooded by customers asking for the price of the product. However, it is also seen that customers ask price even though the seller mentioned the price in his or her posts. Often same price comments are made by customers when the seller has already replied to the product's price in previous queries. Price can also be asked just to compare the price of the product with the physical market price. Moreover, seeking products' prices is more or less similar for both female and male customer-oriented platforms.

Market platforms that have created mandatory rules for mentioning the product price, have made customers more responsive and more engaged through comments. Posts that don't have an asking price, usually don't get approved by the admin of the DMPs. However, there is a tendency for the sellers that they try to avoid mentioning their products' prices and request customers to inbox in the personal message to know the price.

Figure 3: Price queries of customers on Facebook DMPs

Figure 3 shows that female customers inquire more about price queries than male customers on the Facebook market platform. Out of 203 price queries, 77.48% are found from female customers and only 22.51% are found from male customers.

4.3.2 Bargaining

Facebook DMPs are found to be a good place for customers as they can bargain through comments with the sellers on their asking price. Out of 620 comments analyzed from the 10 market platforms, 104 bargaining-related comments (see *Table 5*) are detected. It is also observed that the male customers mostly bargain compared to the female customers. Moreover, very few comments are found where female customers are found to negotiate or bargain with the products price, delivery charge or the quality of the product.

Bargaining is a very common and accepted query for Bangladeshi DMPs. Facebook is also made it easy for customers by providing suggestion queries such as “is the price negotiable?” or “is the price fixed?” These two suggestions indicate customers can negotiate the product’s asking price with the sellers. Usually, sellers request the customers to negotiate in their inboxes. However, customers use bargaining queries to check if they can reduce the product’s price slightly.

Unfortunately, it can also be noted that bargaining questions are often used to discourage customers from wanting to buy products. For example, a smartphone post listed on a platform by BDT ten thousand. If a customer comments on that post at a bargain price of BDT five thousand, it will be less attractive to the next buyers and as a result, they ask for a price less than BDT five thousand. To stop receiving these types of Bargaining and Negotiating comments, sellers often seem to mention that their asking price is fixed and kindly not comment if any customer doesn't agree with the price.

Figure 4: Bargaining inquiries of customers

From *Figure 4*, it is also found that female customers are less interested in negotiating/ bargaining than male customers while choosing a product on the Facebook market platform.

4.5.3 Query for Availability

Products availability queries varieties of queries customers asked through comments to know whether the listed product is available for sale when at the moment when they are commenting. Customers often log in to Facebook in their free time and if a post is published before their login, customers (if they are interested in that product) often get confused to decide purchase decisions as usually sellers often sell only 1 product through 1 post. Therefore, customers are required to inquire first whether the product is available at that moment.

Moreover, a few queries where customers inquire about a similar product but not the promoted product are also accounted into this category. For example, in a few posts, sellers posted for smartphone back cover and customers inquire about the back cover that supports their phone models are taken as a query for the availability section.

4.3.4 General Query – product-related i.e. quality, delivery options, and searching similar products by sharing images

By naming general queries, the customer’s inquiries on product quality, delivery options and searching for similar products by sharing images in the comment section are separated from the inquiries related to price, availability, exchange options and location. All types of customer queries other than the mentioned queries that help customers to know about the products that are uploaded for sale are included in this category. However, all these queries are taken under this ‘general queries’ category due to their small contribution.

The customer’s comments queries on the product’s quality mostly indicated either how long the products are used before or about the condition of the product. Moreover, customers inquire about quality by asking about the country from where the products are made, how durable the products are and so on. Often customers inquire about the user experience of sellers who post used products for sale.

Other than quality-related queries, queries on delivery and courier are also listed. In Bangladesh, most of the products are delivered through courier service by the sellers and sellers include the delivery cost with the product’s price. Therefore, customers often get curious to know about the delivery options and time so that they can reduce costs and time.

4.3.5 Mocking & Irrelevant

About 40 comments (see *Table 5*) are collected about mocking or irrelevance to the product posted by sellers. Here, mocking refers to comments about whether customers make fun of the seller or his products funnily or cruelly. And, irrelevant comments are comments that do not mean any search for products.

When customers ask for a product for a higher price than usual or the post creator cleverly hides it, customers start writing ridiculous comments on posts that could mean that the buyer who bought the product may be deceived. However, it has also been noticed that the most popular groups where customer engagement is relatively high and the admin and moderator are mostly inactive (i.e. Recycle Bin and Buys and Bangladesh Sales), increase the amount of fun in the comments section of the post. Unfortunately, whenever comments about satire are appreciated by other users or customers, the posts get encouraged and more sarcastic comments are commented on by Facebook users. As a result, jokes destroy the real need and message of a product post.

Additionally, there are also a significant amount of irrelevant comments that made no sense with product posts. For example, people post job advertisements online, encourage others to get paid for free from a mobile financial service (spamming), and irrelevant questions that don't try to find answers to the posts.

Figure 5: Mocking and irrelevant queries of customers

Figure 5 shows that Mocking and irrelevant comments are mostly commented on by male users whereas it has been found that mocking in female user posts is very rare on Facebook DMPs.

4.3.6 Inbox, following or interested

Several customers commented on the posts requesting sellers to knock them out in private messages so they could personally discuss questions about their products. Customers have made the following or interested comments that indicate that customers are interested in the posts and would like to receive updates from other customer comments about the product. Here, inbox, follow or interesting means almost the same thing customers are interested in buying the product but they are monitoring the questions asked by other people in the posts.

4.3.7 Recommendation

Users have been found in a post tagging (tag recommendation) their Facebook friends who can purchase these products or look for similar products on Facebook’s marketing platform. Usually, customers discuss their needs with their friends. So, whenever their friends see these kinds of products that can meet their needs, they tag them in their product posts. Through the tagging option, those potential customers can get notifications directly and see the details of the post.

Figure 6: Recommendations made by customers

Figure 6 shows that rarely do female customers recommend products to their friends and family, while male customers voluntarily recommend their friends by tagging their products at the bottom of the post on Facebook DMPs.

4.3.8 Query for exchange – Lower products plus cash offers

Adequate amounts of queries are detected where sellers want to sell their products but customers comment to find out if there is any possibility of exchanging products with customers. Users who sell their products simply because they don't like the product model accept offers of products that can meet their needs if they find their exchange offer. Moreover, customers also provide cash with the products, if their products are less valuable than the seller’s products.

Figure 7: Exchange queries of customers

Figure 7 shows that out of 26 customers (see Table-5) who commented queries for exchange, it is found that male customers are more interested and engaged in exchange offers than female customers on Facebook DMPs.

4.3.9 Positive or supportive comments and product-related Opinion

The category of queries contains positive or supportive comments and product-related opinions. Several queries are detected where customers positively encouraged and supported the sellers for selling a product on what they have personal experience of using those products. Their products related suggestions and opinions are also included in this section.

4.3.10 Promoting own products

Several comments are counted from the posts in this section that are not made by any potential customers of that posts. Customers commented on several product posts promoting their similar own products, whenever they found similar product posts on the Facebook market platform. This kind of comment is given to attract customers through a reduced price or offering better products. Although these comments don't disrupt the demand for the main product's posts, they often create arguments and bargaining options for the post's products.

Figure 8: Own product promotion of customers

Promoting own products on other sellers' posts are made by adding image and product details. Out of 21 comments in total, these types of comments are made mostly by male users compared to female users (shown in figure 8).

4.3.11 Location queries

Location inquiries are primarily conducted by customers living outside of Dhaka City or on products they need to check (i.e. smartphones, laptops) by physically visiting the seller's location before making purchasing decisions. Customers conduct location-related inquiries to decide what costs to incur if they visit the seller's location. Because after visiting the seller's location, if the products are less interesting, the cost of visiting the customer's location can be a loss for customers. Location inquiries are performed primarily by male clients.

4.3.12 Negative comments – i.e. overpriced and others

Fortunately, negative comments are rarely found in the study's analysis, but sellers receive negative comments through social media regardless of how bad or bad their product is. It is inevitable. The survey found a wide variety of comments where customers commented that the products could be found at exorbitant prices and low prices in the local market. Too many negative comments turn commentators into mockery. As a result, when ridicule gets praise from other Facebook users and potential customers, lots of other users start ridiculing and disrupting the seller's posts. However, several comments have been included as negative comments such as 'the product is too bad, don't buy it, 'the unavailability of the spare parts, 'the seller is not trustworthy and so on.

4.4 Summary of results

4.4.1 Information shared by sellers

The study results that there are 51 male sellers and 29 female sellers who posted their product posts on the 10 Facebook DMPs. Out of the total of 80 posts, 51 sellers mentioned their product's price in their post's caption. Unfortunately, out of 80 posts analyzed, only 47.5% or (38) posts are found where sellers provide sufficient information about their products.

Male sellers mention the price of the products and are found to provide sufficient information on their product's posts on Facebook DMPs. They are mostly found to sell electronic products, i.e. smartphones, laptops, motorbikes, cars and other electronic gadgets.

Female sellers don't mention the price of the products and share very limited information about their products on Facebook DMPs. They mostly sell their products on female platforms and encourage customers to ask queries on private messaging. They sell used or unused women's products such as women's clothing and cosmetics on the platforms.

4.4.2 The common queries for Bangladeshi customers

Table 6: List of common queries found in the study results

a. Queries on price	b. Bargaining with the price	c. Query for Availability
d. General Query – product-related i.e. quality	e. Mocking & Irrelevant	f. Inbox, Following or interested
g. Recommendation	h. The query for exchange – lower products plus cash offers	i. Positive or supportive comments and product-related Opinion
j. Promoting own products	k. Location	l. Negative comments – Overpriced

Out of 620 comments, Bangladeshi customers mostly ask 12 types of queries (see details in *Tables- 5 & 6*) on the Facebook market platform before purchasing any products they feel interested in. The customers mostly seek price and Bargaining queries along with other queries.

Male customers mostly bargain, mock, write irrelevant and negative comments and inquire about products whether products are available and offer exchange offers, while female customers mostly ask price-related queries on the Facebook market platform. However, male customers mostly recommend products by tagging their Facebook friends compared to female customers. On the other hand, Female customers are found more interested in inquiring about products through private messages.

5. Discussion

Regarding the analysis of DMPs - Previous researchers referred to Facebook sales groups as social commerce and categorized them as a subset of next-generation e-commerce in which users (sellers and buyers) conducted business activities or transactions via social media platforms ([Wang and Zhang, 2012](#)). However, the recently introduced Facebook function "Facebook Marketplace" (which plays a direct role in the transaction itself, from managing payments to ensuring that products or services are delivered) has created a need to differentiate Facebook sales groups. Furthermore, Facebook sales groups employ several similar conceptual terms, including "social shopping," "collaborative commerce," and "collaborative shopping." [Friedrich \(2015\)](#) defined collaborative shopping, collaborative commerce, and social shopping as social commerce terms that can be used interchangeably in his research. However, according to [Stephen and Toubia \(2010\)](#), when the term "social shopping" is used, it refers to the activities of buyers, whereas "social commerce" is more associated with sellers. However, through literary reviews, all of these researchers attempted to create an overall generalized term that can reflect the overall activities of Facebook sales groups that involve administrators, buyers, and sellers. As a result, this study refers to these Facebook sales groups as platforms, because they establish contact with buyers and sellers while avoiding the time required to complete the transaction. Furthermore, the study suggests referring to the Facebook sales group as "DMPs" because these platforms are virtual and are maintained by administrators (usually evacuated when transactions are confirmed). Furthermore, the platform can be viewed as the sum of the space for the exchange of information, products, or services between the seller, the customer, and the community that communicates on (inquiries about) the platform. It is critical to recognize that the community is an essential component of the DMP. The potential value of DMPs will be very low if there is no community. In general, DMPs sell the products and services of sellers to serve customers and thus provide them as a community. As [Watts](#) defined in 2020, the community plays an important role on the platform. On these platforms, today's salesperson could be tomorrow's customer, or today's customer could be tomorrow's salesperson. Next, the findings are also consistent with [Gatautis \(2017\)](#), as platform administrators/moderators can only act as digital intermediaries, approving product posts, controlling members, monitoring posts and comments, and managing general platform settings. Therefore, in the context of the preceding discussion, Facebook's buy/sell groups can also be referred to as a DMP or a Facebook digital market platform, as these platforms provide the same services to specific communities that are established based on their own needs and demands. Furthermore, the admins create, monitor, and operate these market platforms, which are managed by the moderators. The general members are usually the buyers and sellers. Sellers may post their used or unused product posts following the Facebook community guidelines and rules established by the admins/moderators. These posts typically include a caption (information about the product for sale) and images of the product. If, on the other hand, a customer is interested in viewing the sellers' posts from the market platform, they can either send a direct message to the sellers or post a comment as a query to know more. However, these Facebook DMPs only serve to bring together sellers and buyers in one location where sellers can post their products for sale and buyers can make decisions based on images and information about the products. These platforms, like [Facebook and Commerce \(2020\)](#), lack payment systems and delivery services

authorized by Facebook. Furthermore, most members do not know each other, but they joined these platforms because they share similar interests. Unauthorized payment service transactions between buyers and sellers will always pose risks. According to recent studies, online shoppers continue to prioritize product performance, financial loss, time wasted, and purchase disappointment (Griffin & Viehland, 2012). According to Chua and Wareham (2004), online platforms have been used to sell illegal, stolen, and recalled products [Bort, J. (2016); Oravec, (2014)] to carry out prepayment scams (Sundararajan, 2017), and despite committing violent crimes (albeit infrequently) (Oravec, 2014). In this case, the seller will move to a new buyer to respond to or comment on "queries for availability" requests as a potential new buyer. However, the buyers can also change their opinion once they get more information about the product through private information.

Regarding sharing information by sellers - Hanna et. al. (2011) stated that many companies face difficulties even though they (as sellers) actively access social media market platforms and practice online promotions. The challenge is that, while identifying existing needs and acting on different social networking sites, they fail to realize how social media activities and habits provide effective use of opportunities. However, from these DMPs companies or sellers can obtain many targeted customers. The Facebook DMPs initially sell the products with a sales location with prices, photos and descriptions of the products, which are also known as product descriptions, captions, or subtitles (Moser, Resnick & Schoenebeck, 2017). According to Jeffrey & Hodge (2007), the price is a valuable element that is mentioned by most Bangladeshi sellers, in which men mention the price relative to women on the postings for their products. In addition, the high-quality product descriptions found by Mou, Zhu and Benyoucef (2019) had no significant positive influence on purchasing intentions, but had significant positive effects on cognitive commitment; product emotional commitment; persistent platform engagement and contextual involvement to the product. Unfortunately, Bangladeshi sellers overall do not share enough information about their products, but the male sellers are ahead of the female sellers among those who do.

Regarding Customer Queries - Because of their growing popularity, ease of access, and use, DMPs are becoming unsafe for clients. The risk factor may affect customers' use of online platforms and have a major impact on online purchase intentions, according to Leerapong and Mardjo (2013). To begin with, purchasing things through Facebook is deemed dangerous due to the lack of precise standards for becoming a Facebook seller. Second, there is no protection for the customer if the seller fails to keep the promise made to him. Fear of loss, fraud and other risks might occur when interacting with foreigners and it makes buying decisions harder for customers. To protect customers against threats, before making purchasing decisions, they ask questions to satisfy themselves. Furthermore, the degree of risk that customers are faced with depends on the subjective certainty of success or failure and the risk involved (consequence) (Jahankhani, 2009). The number of critical moments refers to the loss which would occur if the situation failed. If the risk of buying a product or service is believed too high by the customer, the transaction cannot be completed. Otherwise, by reducing risk or uncertain situations, customers can initiate risk reduction behaviours (Jahankhani, 2012), and this way customers can reduce invisible risks in the future using the comment section of product messages. The study also found certain differences in queries among other social platforms (i.e. Twitter). In 2017, 565 tweets and retweets are researched, along with 1392 replies from the Twitter handles of Starbucks. The author found six kinds: information, apology and support, positive comments, questions and inquiries, chitchat and gratitude while the two questions most frequently asked by customers in Bangladesh relate to pricing and bargaining. The findings of Bakos (1997) may be similar in that they need to ask more price questions and to bargain can reflect customer convenience to compare products provided by different online sellers. It reduces to some extent customer search costs, which limits the difference in prices between online sellers and eventually increases competitiveness (Bakos, 1997). This study also found that price has the greatest impact on the buying and selling of a commodity (from the viewpoint of the customer). As customers have a rational budget and income, the price and bargaining queries among Bangladeshi customers are the two most frequently searched queries. In addition to price, general

queries consisting of the product, quality, and delivery query options; availability queries; interchange query; location search queries are also found in the study. In addition, customers of the product items can share positive opinions that encourage sellers to provide the right information and help other customers make purchasing decisions. A Deloitte US study has also shown that 62% of US customers read customer reviews online and 98% think they are enough reliable. 80% of customers said reading these reviews would impact their willingness to purchase (Ioană, & Stoica, 2014). Customers also found themselves to be interested in writing an inbox, to decide later or to be updated from other customers' subsequent comments. Moreover, the study found similar findings to Dholakia et al. (2004) regarding the recommendation to friends in commenting on posts, who said that social media platforms help maintain interpersonal connectivity between social media online users to make contacts and maintain them in a way that provides social support. In the last analysis, even a small amount of negative information has shown significant impacts on customer attitudes (Schlosser, 2005). The three types of unfortunate comments found in the product reviews section of digital marketing platforms are negative commentary, mocking and irrelevant comments. These comments have the potential to influence customer decisions and prevent sellers from launching new products in the future.

6. Suggested solution

6.1 Recommendations of the study

The sellers and customers of DMPs are encouraged to follow the recommendation to make the sales process much easier.

I. Recommendations for sellers and marketers of DMP

a. **Choosing the right market platforms**

Sellers should first choose the appropriate market platform to sell their products quickly. When selecting a DMP to post their products on, sellers should look at previous posts on market platforms created by other sellers to see if the platform has a sufficient number of members and customers. Furthermore, products should be posted following the relevant DMP. For instance, there are many market platforms for laptop computers, but if a seller lists their laptop products on a centralized market platform for smartphones, the possibilities of selling laptop computers with smartphones are little to none. As a result, before posting a product for sale, sellers should research and comprehend the DMPs.

Figure 9: Suggestions for sellers' sharing of product information

b. Suggesting model for post’s information

The primary goal of sellers posting their sales posts is to sell things on the market platform. It's difficult to attract the proper customers quickly if sellers and marketers don't provide enough information about the products. As a result of the analysis and observations of posting product information on Facebook DMPs, all sellers and admins are advised to follow the model below to reach the correct customers and be credible with the proper product information. Furthermore, the model (in *Figure 9*) has been designed to assist customers in obtaining the most often-asked questions so that the appropriate customers may easily engage with the Sellers.

c. Ignore the mocking and negative comments

Sellers should not respond to mocking and negative comments as customer relationship opportunities to engage and respond, but rather should review or ignore these comments so that they do not draw attention. People may refrain from making further negative comments if they see that their comments are being ignored.

ii. Recommendations for customers of DMP

a. Read the comments and check the images of the products carefully

Customers are advised not to directly list queries or make purchase decisions as soon as they see a sales post for their favourite products on Facebook DMPs, as the products may fall short of their expectations. As a result, it is recommended that they first read the information about the product provided by the seller and carefully examine the images to determine if there is any defect visible in the image.

Figure 10: Suggestion for customers to make the purchase decisions

b. Compare products details from available sources

Today, it is very simple to find true information about any product by searching on Google or YouTube. To identify any information about any technical product, such as a smartphone, YouTube is a great platform where customers can see how the products look and feel while being unboxed. For general information, Google

search can be very useful for customers who know little about their favourite products. Customers should, however, compare the information provided by the seller on the market platform to the information available on Google (See Figure 10).

c. Search for inquired query in the comment section

During data collection, it was discovered that customers frequently ask similar questions without checking previous comments made by other customers to which the seller had already responded. As a result, a list of queries is compiled solely on 'price,' with customers listing the price queries repeatedly. It can be extremely stressful for sellers to respond to all of the inquiries. As a result, it is recommended that before making any inquiries, customers check to see if the seller has responded to similar inquiries.

d. Ask queries

We know that '*Prevention is better than cure*'. Customers should ask their questions first in the comments section if they can't find the questions they need from the product comment list. In addition, they are advised not to knock sellers directly through 'inbox' messages (unless sellers are not known to customers), but posting a query in the comments section may help other customers find answers to their questions, and avoid additional charges or fraud. This can help the customer get acquainted with other observers or customers if possible. After getting a satisfactory answer to the question, customers should check the seller's profile as checking the profile often can help to understand the nature of the seller. Finally, we can inbox the seller of the personal conversation needed to provide personal details and purchase products. The whole process is described in the following flowchart in figure 10.

6.2 Conclusion

Although Facebook lacks traditional e-commerce tools, the platform's unique characteristics make it convenient for both sellers and customers, allowing transactions between strangers in similar geographic locations. Furthermore, all parties involved in Facebook with these DMPs must improve for these platforms to work and be reliable for everyone. The study's goal is to identify common customer questions and general trends in sellers (distributed by gender) sharing pricing and product information to assist customers in making more informed decisions.

The first objective of the research is to analyze the DMPs. The research found that these platforms are Facebook sales groups ruled and controlled by administrators and moderators, where people usually gather from similar communities or from product interests to buy and sell their products.

The second objective of the study is to analyze the Bangladeshi sellers of those platforms, to identify the information shared in the products' descriptions to help the decision-making process easier for the customers. The study found that most of the sellers list their post's mentioning the price and sufficient information in the description, especially the males. When females are less interested to mention the price and detailed info of their products, rather they encourage customers to message their queries privately.

The final objective of this research is to analyze the comments to generalize the most common queries made by Bangladeshi customers that help them to make their purchase decisions. The research found 12 frequently asked questions and comments, and among them, price, bargaining, availability, recommendations, and negative & mocking are highly significant comments for Bangladeshi customers.

According to the study, while male sellers share a lot of product information as well as the asking price, female sellers are less interested in disclosing information and prefer to discuss their products privately. Even though the majority of surveyed sellers provided sufficient information, customers continued to ask a large number of questions, either to learn the same information that is described in the product description or to learn new information. Among the twelve queries detected by the analysis, queries for price; bargain queries; queries for availability, general queries (i.e. quality-related); and mocking & irrelevant comments are the most frequently asked by Bangladeshi customers in the comments section of DMPs to make purchase decisions.

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Appendix

Table 7. Description of selected DMPs

SL No.	Name of the Platform	Web Address of the Platforms	Type	Focused customer of the platform	Admin no.	Moderator no.	Est. date	Total Members
1.	Recycle Bin	https://www.facebook.com/groups/ourrecyclebin/permalink/937130073523729	Private Group	Both	5	16	Oct 5, 2020	1000k
2.	Mobile Buy and Sell Bazar	https://www.facebook.com/groups/mobilebuysellbazar	Private	Both	2	2	August 5, 2019	256.1k
3.	Used/Unused Products Sell	https://www.facebook.com/groups/311625992838469	Public	Female	2	5	April 26, 2019	45.8k
4.	Buy And Sell Bangladesh	https://www.facebook.com/groups/ar.gadget.official.group	Private Group	Both	4	5	July 3, 2017	222.1k
5.	GPU Market Bangladesh	https://www.facebook.com/groups/OnlyGPU	Private Group	Both	1	3	Dec 30, 2017	37.5k
6.	Buy Sell Exchange (ক্রয়-বিক্রয়-এক্সচেঞ্জ)	https://www.facebook.com/groups/169503123174285	Private Group	Both	10	7	Jan 31, 2019	536.3k
7.	Bd Bike Sell Bazar	https://www.facebook.com/groups/1798263223778462/about	Private Group	Both	10	1	Dec 6, 2018	64.2k
8.	Online Product Sell & Exchange™	https://www.facebook.com/groups/cellcazar/?notif_id=1614651610348312&notif_t=group_r2j_approved&ref=notif	Private Group	Both	3	1	Aug 19, 2011	87.6k
9.	Sell UNLOVED Stuffs 🍷	https://www.facebook.com/groups/1945934568756493/about	Private Group	Both	3	3	Jan 2, 2021	16.7k
10.	Used Cars For Sale in Bangladesh (UCSB)	https://www.facebook.com/groups/kzeeshan/about	Private Group	Both	5	3	June 8, 2020	213.9k